

Applications Of Nutrigenomics in Livestock

R Selvam

Livestock Farm Complex, Veterinary College and Research Institute,
Tirunelveli – 627 358, Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract

Nutrigenomics is a science which analyses the effects of nutrients on the expression of an individual's genetic makeup. It includes three "omics" viz., Transcriptomics, Proteomics and Metabolomics. It analyses how nutrition influence gene expression, metabolic pathways and disease development which implies the possibility to change the way of feeding the livestock and poultry. Nutrigenomics combines diversified fields such as nutrition, bioinformatics, molecular biology, genomics and epigenomics. The main function of nutrigenomics is to develop the feeds that can be matched to genotypes of animals for a better production, reproduction and health. Nutrigenomics in livestock can applied in improvement of growth rate, milk production and composition, feed usage and carcass composition, disease resistance, enhanced reproductive and prolificacy enhancement. Generally, nutrigenomics can bridge the gap between genetic profile and feeding for better conversion efficiency in livestock production and reproduction. The challenge for nutrigenomics research is to target the genes involved in the major diseases. Nutrigenomics has various benefits and applications as biomarkers, developing strategies for prevention of diseases, designing functional foods, identification of pathways and candidate genes, improving production and reproduction and make a pathway towards personalized nutrition.

Introduction

Nutrigenomics is a science which analyses the effects of nutrients on the expression of an individual's genetic makeup. Nutrigenomics is broadly defined as the relationship between nutrients, diet, and gene expression. It deals with role of nutrient on gene expression. Nutrigenomics analyse how nutrients affect genes (influence on gene expression and function) and how genes affect diet (how an individual responds to nutrients). Nutrigenomics includes effect of nutrients on synthesis of mRNA (Transcriptomics), protein synthesis (Proteomics) and metabolite production (Metabolomics). Nutrigenomic approaches will enhance researcher's abilities to maintain animal health, optimize performance and improve milk and meat quality. By targeting the specific gene through nutritional manipulation, it may be possible to get the desired livestock performance. This article reviews the applications of nutrigenomics and how the nutrients influence the health, production and reproduction in livestock.

The functions of Nutrigenomics

The main function of nutrigenomics is to develop the feeds that can be matched to genotypes of animals for a better production, reproduction and health. Diet with other environmental factors can produce epigenetic changes that make certain genes switched on or off. Nutrigenomics provide a basis for dietary management of maintenance and protection of health. The major nutrients such as folate, choline, and vitamins B2, B6, B12, and vitamin A regulate gene expression. Diets with a high glycaemic index load have also been associated with gene expression, for example the association between a high glycaemic index diet and exaggerated polymorphism of the Adiponectin gene, contributing to insulin resistance and diabetes type II. The application of single nucleotide polymorphism clarifies the different responses to same nutrient by different individuals and explores the effect of genetic variation on the interaction between diet and disease.

Application of Nutrigenomics in Livestock and Poultry

Nutrigenomics in livestock can applied in improvement of growth rate, milk production and composition, feed usage and carcass composition, disease resistance, enhanced reproductive and prolificacy enhancement. Generally, nutrigenomics can bridge the gap between genetic profile and feeding for better conversion efficiency in livestock production and reproduction. It is possible to measure the effects of certain nutritional supplements and how they alter the gene interaction of the body using gene chips that contain the genetic code of animal.

Nutrigenomics in Dairy Cattle

There are several transcription factors with great potential for nutrigenomic interventions to modify the metabolism of dairy cows to improve performance, health, and milk quality. Among these, PPAR stand out as the most promising. The fatty acids, particularly Long Chain Fatty Acid, are the most potent nutrigenomic compounds in the diet. Nutrigenomic effects of those LCFA are striking in vitro but appear more modest in vivo. Nutrigenomics data produced in dairy cows clearly underscores the fact that the current system to build diets for high-producing dairy cows is blind to the nutrigenomic effects of dietary compounds that, by affecting the metabolism of the animal, likely modify its dietary requirements. A better knowledge of the metabolism of long-chain fatty acids would help in designing daily rations for transient high-yielding dairy cows. Instead of supplemental fat for the fresh cow, the provision of absorbable amino acids and glucogenic precursors, such as absorbed glucose, propionate and isobutyrate, should be emphasized. By application of the inhibitor trans-10, cis-12 CLA, milk fat production could be reduced during the critical periods of dairy cows in a controlled manner.

Nutrigenomics in Swine

Diet with glutamine supplement is better for a piglet to modulate the expression of genes that are necessary for intestinal metabolism and function. Low protein content in diet increases the intramuscular fat by regulating heart fatty acid-binding protein or H-FABP, peroxisome proliferator activated receptor γ or PPAR γ gene which enhances the quality of pig meet. Supplemental CLA in swine diets, by activating PPAR γ -responsive genes in adipose tissue, stimulates fat oxidation in the peroxisomes, reducing both voluntary feed intake and whole-body fat content.

Nutrigenomics in Poultry

In Poultry, the lipid metabolism in female chicken of two broiler strain could be regulated by nicotinic acid. Transcriptional regulator of gene involved in lipid oxidation and antioxidant gene expression could be induced via vitamin E diet which has an effect to reduce stress and enhance meat quality and can increase immune protection against bacterial lipopolysaccharide associated infection in chicken.

Effects of selenium on gene expression

Selenium deficiencies can influence the patterns of protein synthesis in mice by regulating the expression of specific genes at the transcriptional level. Genes that were up-regulated by selenium deficiencies in mice included those associated with stress responses, cell cycling and growth, and cell adherence. At the same time, genes that were down-regulated included those associated with detoxification mechanisms, selenoprotein production, oxidative stress protection, and lipid transport. It is important to note that these changes in gene expression can be used to account for many of the outward phenotypic characteristics of selenium deficiencies. In swine, poultry and ruminants, organic dietary selenium can enhance milk yield, egg production and growth performance. The role of selenium in reproductive performance in poultry seems to be dependent on both selenium source and length of supplementation. Maintaining flocks on diets supplemented with organic selenium for a long period of time improves egg production in broilers and layers. While the effects of nutrition on fertility are only partially understood, modern nutrigenomics will undoubtedly play a key role in developing strategies for addressing some of the limitations in reproductive performance.

Effects of Vitamins on gene expression

Vitamin A exerts its regulatory function in the form of retinol and retinoic acid. The important target tissues are in the adrenal glands, testes, cerebellum, kidneys, prostate, cerebral cortex, skin and the viscera. After retinoic acid binds to its receptor, it will stimulate the transcription and translation of

vitamin A-responsive genes, including some involved in cell differentiation (growth hormone, glycerophosphate dehydrogenase and leptin production among others). Deficient vitamin A status was found to negatively influence hepatic PEPCK gene expression in mice. Like those of retinoic acid, the actions of *active vitamin D* are mediated by nuclear hormone receptors. The vitamin D receptor directly binds to DNA at vitamin D responsive elements as a homodimer or heterodimer to activate gene transcription. Ligand binding to the vitamin D receptor forms a complex of coactivators that modulates gene expression in different cell types. A role for *biotin* in gene expression has been recognized by the significant depression of ornithine transcarboxylase gene expression in biotin deficiency. The consequent loss of enzyme activity is the basis for hyperammonemia.

Nutrigenomics and Diseases

Cis-9, trans-11 CLA or ruminic acid, present in milk, has been found to have anticarcinogenic effect in rats, where it was found to be capable of reducing the incidence of mammary cancer. Over-expression of cyclo-oxygenase-2 (COX-2) is thought to be one of the causative factors of breast tumour genesis. By repressing the activation of COX-2 transcription, mixtures of CLA isomers were able to counterbalance carcinogenic inflammation in cell culture. In the case of colon cancer cells exclusively the *trans-10, cis-12* CLA was capable of inhibiting cell cycle progression via induction of a cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor, the p21. The *cis-9, trans-11* CLA compound have also proved to have antiatherogenic, antiobesity and antidiabetic characteristics against type I and type II diabetes. To prevent obesity and type II diabetes, the direct modulation of gene expression by nutrients is also a potential mechanism. The influence of diet on the phenotypic manifestation in some cases is drastically determinant. The prenatal nutrient supply may influence not only the development of adipose tissue, but also the colour of the offspring.

Challenges and Opportunities

The challenge for nutrigenomics research is to target the genes involved in the major diseases. The bioactive ingredients of food may turn on some genes and simultaneously turn off other genes involved in a disease. The success of this science will require meaningful biomarkers. The application of different molecular biological techniques in transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolic and microarray technology in livestock species as nutrigenomics research tool will provide gene expression patterns variation and explanations for complex regulatory interactions between nutrients and genes.

Optimization of productivity and efficiency in nutrition utilization could be possible. However, there is limitation in nutrigenomics information how to effectively analyse and correlate genes and

nutrition conversion in livestock production. Molecular genetics tools having substantial impact in the future include DNA-based tests for genes or markers are affecting traits that are difficult to measure, such as meat quality and disease resistance. This could be used as an opportunity to breed for improvement of productivity, such as product quality, increasing animal welfare, disease resistance, disease receptivity and reducing environmental impact.

This approach will help the breeder or researcher for a precise determination of nutrient beneath specific condition. The level of expression for a same nutrition is different in individuals. For example, the changes in plasma cholesterol can be due the dietary of cholesterol; however, this expression is dependent upon the individual. Possible to change the way we feed and manage livestock and poultry that the nutrition is genotype dependent and nutrient could bring expression of genotype.

Nutrigenomics can only provide part of the solution in response to non-genetic factors involved in an individual's health and production. Environmental, cultural and economic factors also play an essential role in individual food choices and accessibility. Malnutrition in the form of under nutrition or obesity can also modify gene expression and genome stability, resulting in changes in phenotype, and hence it is difficult to choose one population as a reference. The availability of genomic information is important to determine a specific nutrient under specific condition.

Conclusion

Nutrigenomics is the most promising research field in the area of livestock to develop feeds that can be matched to genotypes of animals for a better production and health. It includes three 'omics' viz., Transcriptomics, Proteomics and Metabolomics. It analyses how nutrition influence gene expression, metabolic pathways and disease development which implies the possibility to change the way of feeding the livestock and poultry. Nutrigenomics combines diversified fields such as nutrition, bioinformatics, molecular biology, genomics, functional genomics, epidemiology, and epigenomics. These new approaches highlight the relevant role of genetics-nutrition interactions on different physiological and metabolic processes with a high impact on economically relevant traits as meat and milk quality. Nutrigenomics has various benefits and applications as biomarkers, developing strategies for prevention of diseases, designing functional foods, identification of pathways and candidate genes, improving production and reproduction and make a pathway towards personalized nutrition. Nutrigenomics approaches promise to set new standards for nutritional research and will revolutionize the views of nutrient requirements and interactions. Nutrigenomics will improve the capacity to maintain animal health, production and reproduction performances. In Nutrigenomics the global sharing of knowledge

of expertise from various fields is required. The process of forming international alliances, development of a virtual center for organizing communications that promote resources sharing and creation of databases are essential.

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